

Harvis {^-} Aircraft Dynamic Rerouting Support

Human Aircraft
Roadmap for Virtual
Intelligent System

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OBJECTIVES

In order for **Single Pilot Operations** to become a reality, not only is a complete reorganization of the tasks between ground and aircrafts needed, but also the integration of **more supportive tools in the cockpit**. This work introduces a **cockpit digital assistant** committed to helping the pilot reroute the aircraft during the **approach and landing phases** in SPO, which can lead to stressful situations that increase the pilot's workload, by **anticipating** the possible variations in the arrival routes and providing the most likely arrival trajectories that the ATC would suggest.

PROPOSED CONCEPT

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For this work, a **Deep Learning** model has been created based on **Multi Layer Perceptron** capable of **determining the approach trajectory of aircraft** flying from Toulouse to Seville, 30 minutes prior to the expected landing time, using only METAR information.

RESULTS

Overall accuracy of the validation: **86.64%**

Experiments with the **predictive model** show an accuracy, recall and F1-score **higher than 0.9**.

Table 1: Model prediction results.

Arrival Point	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Test set
Rotex	0.94	0.97	0.96	29
Santa	0.92	0.85	0.88	18
Weighted Av.	0.94	0.94	0.94	

CONCLUSIONS

- ✈ For the model's improvement, a bigger dataset is needed for training and validation stages.
- ✈ Apply the proposed Model to more complex Airports.
- ✈ Use **Recursive Neuronal Networks** architectures to predict the entire approach trajectory.

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